

ANALYSIS OF VALUE EFFECTIVENESS MACHINE USING OVERALL EQUIPMENT EFFECTIVENESS (OEE) METHOD AS AN IMPROVEMENT TO MINIMIZE SIX BIG LOSSES IN STEEL INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Machine is very vital and important role in the production line manufacturing of steel industry. The machine maintenance system has a constraint on the old machine which caused the level of productivity decreased. The purpose of this research is to measure and find the level of machine effectiveness, also to offer solutions to improve the effectiveness of the machine by calculating Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) which consists of several components such as availability ratio, performance ratio, and quality ratio of the production process. Further, to be able to acknowledge the most influential losses in the production line and assist the company to decide its policy appropriately as an effort to repair the machine using Six Big Losses. The OEE calculation of the Electrolytic Cleaning Line 1 (ECL-1) in Plant Cold Rolling Mill (CRM) is 64.91% which is still below the standard Word Class OEE of 85%. While the significant losses result in Reduce Speed Losses factor of 19.80%. Based on analysis using fishbone diagram, it shows machine speed decreasing by ECL-1 that is caused by factor of machine, material, and method.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The industry world manufacturing is growing up very rapidly. Every company always makes change in a continuous improvement in each department to be able to compete in the era of globalization, especially in the production line. production line has various things that must always be improved, including equipment and machines that support the production process. the effort to repair on the manufacturing world, in terms of equipment and machine are to increase the utilization of existing equipment as optimal as possible. Utilization of existing equipment on the average manufacturing industry is half of the real machine capability [1]. A company makes a lot of improvements. but in the fact, many company did not focused on the root causes and lot of waste occur. Eventually many losses occur such as time, costs, and most problems. thus, a method is needed that can be increase according to the problem of lack of equipment productivity. In this research implement Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) method is a method that uses several manufacturing units which are then divided into 3 important parameters such as availability, performance rate and quality rate [2]. So that the component of OEE is a key index for a production [3]. In the OEE concept is measuring the ability of machine by showing scope of specific improvements. Where the statistical data collected from output plant becomes useful information for increasing the area. [4]In finding identification which the most significant causes of failure of OEE values, researchers used Six Big Losses. Where the determinants are categorized into 3, namely downtime losses, speed losses, and defect losses. [5]This research was conducted

on the company PT. XYZ which is a manufacturing company that produces steel. In the production line, the engine has decreased the level of productivity due to the age of the old machine. To be able to make improvements in accordance with the problems that occur by calculating OEE which is part of the Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) method and using Six Big Losses to determine the losses that most influence the low OEE value, then analyze the causes of losses by using the fishbone diagram and provide solutions relating to the losses that occur.

2. BASIC THEORY

2.1 Total Productive Maintenance (TPM)

Total Productive Maintenance is a productive maintenance development from America which was adopted later by Japan. In the technique TPM is used to be a maintenance team in an organization that involves human resources in a strategy-based on company designed to maximize the effectiveness of equipment by developing a comprehensive maintenance production system. The main objective is to realize cost saving through maintenance and increased machine productivity. [6]

2.2 Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE)

Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) is a method used to measure the level of effectiveness of the use of a machine tool so that it can provide an overview of whether the equipment has worked optimally or not. OEE is known as one of the applications of the Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) program because this tool can find out the problems in the equipment. In measuring the effectiveness value of an equipment or machine, it can be calculated by the following formula:

$$OEE(\%) = Availability\ Ratio \times Performance\ Efficiency \times Rate\ of\ Quality$$

The effective value of an equipment in Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) according to the Japan Institute of Plan Maintenance (JIPM). In a company must have an ideal value of world class of 85% or more ideal value. In the calculation and measurement using OEE, there are 3 types of losses that are directly related to the production process that must be anticipated, namely:

2.2.1 Availability Ratio

Availability Ratio is the ratio between the actual operating time and the loading time. This value can describe the level of readiness of existing and used tools to operate. Low availability is reflection of poor maintenance. In simple terms and basis for calculating the Availability ratio as follows:

$$Availability\ Ratio(\%) = \frac{Load\ time - downtime}{load\ time} \times 100\%$$

Explanation:

- Loading Time: Time available to carry out the production process
- Downtime: Time lost due to engine damage

2.2.2. Performance Ratio

Performance Ratio is a ratio that describes the ability of equipment in producing goods. Three important factors are needed to calculate performance efficiency, there are:

- Ideal cycle time
- Total output (Output standard + Output non standard)
- Operating Time (Loading time – downtime)

The following is the formula for determining the level of performance efficiency:

$$\text{Performance Rate} = \frac{\text{Ideal cycle time} \times \text{Total Output}}{\text{Operating time}} \times 100\%$$

2.2.3 Quality Ratio

This measurement is used to determine the quality of production, whether a machine can produce products with results or quality determined by the company or not. So, the ability of the machine to produce products that meet these quality requirements depends on the condition of the machine, whether it is ready for use or not. In addition, the capability factor of the operator also plays an important role in every production produced by the machine. The rate of quality is calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Rate of Quality} = \frac{\text{Total output} - \text{Output non standard}}{\text{Total output}} \times 100\%$$

Explanation:

- Total Output : $\text{Output standard} + \text{Output non standard}$
- Output Standard : Products that are in accordance with the specified quality
- Non standard: Products that are in not accordance with the specified quality

2.2.4 Six Big Losses

The purpose of six big losses is to find out the loss factors that provide the biggest contribution in reducing the productivity of machines in the production line. The analysis carried out is that there are large loss factors such as breakdown losses, set up & adjustment, idling and loss losses, reduced speed losses, reduce yield losses, defect losses. [7]

2.2.5 Fishbone Diagram

fishbone diagram is a visual tool such as a fish fin which is used to identify and sort systematically the root causes of different problems so that the diagram can provide several causes of the effects of the biggest problem. [8]

3 RESEACRH METHODS

This research aim is to measure the effectiveness of one machine at the plant of the company PT. XYZ. Using OEE method approach. Researchers make observations in advance to retrieve data. The data obtained are production data, product data, and utilization data of cold rolling mill plants (CRM). After the data is obtained, then do the data processing also analysis of Six big losses are carried out as well as suggestion for improvement for the company.

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Analysis of OEE Result

In determining the formula and measuring the effectiveness of the machine, OEE using 3 aspects are multiplying the value of Availability Ratio, Performance Ratio, and Quality Ratio. So, the following are the results obtained from 3 aspects of OEE:

Table 1 Availability Ratio Results

Month	Operating Time		Loading Time		Availability Ratio (%)		
	Lite	Medium	Lite	Medium	Lite	Medium	Average
January	8,426.25	10,111.50	8,781.25	10,537.50	95.96%	95.96%	95.96%

Month	Operating Time		Loading Time		Availability Ratio (%)		
	Lite	Medium	Lite	Medium	Lite	Medium	Average
February	7,759.50	9,311.40	8,116.00	9,739.20	95.61%	95.61%	95.61%
March	7,601.50	9,121.80	8,203.75	9,844.50	92.66%	92.66%	92.66%
April	8,695.75	10,434.90	9,191.25	11,029.50	94.61%	94.61%	94.61%
Mei	9,522.50	11,427.00	10,571.25	12,685.50	90.08%	90.08%	90.08%
June	9,647.75	11,577.30	10,033.00	12,039.60	96.16%	96.16%	96.16%
Total					94.18%	94.18%	94.18%

This following is the formula used to measure availability ratio and an example of the calculation availability ratio for the Lite type in January 2017:

$$Availability = \frac{Operating\ Time}{Loading\ Time} \times 100\%$$

$$Availability\ Ratio = \frac{8,426.25}{8,781.25}$$

$$= 95,96\%$$

Table 2 Performance Efficiency Results

Month	Total Output (Coil)		Cycle Time (Coil/Minute)	Operating Time (Minute)		Performance Efficiency (%)		
	Lite	Medium		Lite	Medium	Lite	Medium	Average
January	342.71	411.25	Lite: 24.40	84,26.25	10,111.5	99.24%	74.35%	86.79%
February	307.45	368.94		7,759.5	9,311.4	96.68%	72.43%	84.55%
March	259.10	310.91		7,601.5	9,121.8	83.17%	62.31%	72.74%
April	260.73	312.87	Medium: 18.28	8,695.75	10,434.9	73.16%	54.81%	63.98%
Mei	355.39	426.47		9,522.5	11,427	91.06%	68.22%	79.64%
June	366.99	477.88		9,647.75	11,577.3	92.81%	75.46%	88.09%

This following is the formula used to measure performance ratio and an example of the calculation performance efficiency for the Lite type in Mei 2017:

$$Performance\ Efficiency = \frac{Total\ Output \times Cycle\ Time}{Operating\ Time} \times 100\%$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Performance Efficiency} &= \frac{355.39 \times 24.40}{9,522.5} 100\% \\ &= 91.06\% \end{aligned}$$

Table 3 Rate of Quality Results

Month	Total of Good Product (Coil)		Total Production (Coil)		Rate of Quality (%)		
	<i>Lite</i>	<i>Medium</i>	<i>Lite</i>	<i>Medium</i>	<i>Lite</i>	<i>Medium</i>	Average
January	289.43	347.32	342.71	411.25	84.45%	84.45%	84.45%
February	280.50	336.60	307.45	368.94	91.23%	91.23%	91.23%
March	236.76	284.11	259.10	310.91	91.38%	91.38%	91.38%
April	229.17	275.01	260.73	312.87	87.90%	87.90%	87.90%
Mei	267.76	321.32	355.39	426.47	75.34%	75.34%	75.34%
June	359.82	431.78	398.24	477.88	90.35%	90.35%	90.35%

This following is the formula used to measure Rate of Quality and an example of the calculation Rate of Quality for the Lite type in March 2017:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate of Quality} &= \frac{\text{Total of Good Product}}{\text{Total Production}} \times 100\% \\ \text{Rate of Quality} &= \frac{236.76}{259.10} \times 100\% \\ &= 91.38\% \end{aligned}$$

After getting value of the Availability Ratio, Performance Efficiency, and Rate of Quality, then the value of Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) can be calculated every month to determine the effectiveness of the use Electrolytic Cleaning Line 1 (ECL-1) machines in Cold Rolling Mill Plant (CRM) The formula used to calculate OEE is:

$$\text{OEE} = \text{Availability Ratio} \times \text{Performance Efficiency} \times \text{Rate of Quality}$$

Table 4 Overall Equipment Effectiveness

Month	Availability Ratio (%)	Performance Efficiency (%)	Rate of Quality (%)	OEE (%)
January	95.96%	86.79%	84.45%	70.34%
February	95.61%	84.55%	91.23%	73.75%
March	92.66%	72.74%	91.38%	61.59%
April	94.61%	63.98%	87.90%	53.21%
Mei	90.08%	79.64%	75.34%	54.05%
June	96.16%	88.09%	90.35%	76.53%
Average	94.18%	79.30%	86.78%	64.91%

Whereas the more detailed description of the Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) results for each type of product contained in the CRM plant are:

Table 5 Product Types of Overall Equipment Effectiveness Results

Month	Product Types		Average
	Lite	Medium	
January	80.42%	60.25%	70.34%
February	84.33%	63.18%	73.75%
March	70.42%	52.76%	61.59%
April	60.84%	45.58%	53.21%
Mei	61.80%	46.30%	54.05%
June	87.51%	65.56%	76.53%
Average	74.22%	55.60%	64.91%

Based on the results of the calculation of data, the Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) value was obtained on the ECL-1 machine on the CRM plant which was 64.91%.

Figure 1 Graph of Overall Equipment Effectiveness ECL-1 Machine

According to the figure 4.5, Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) on the ECL-1 machine has a rather bad value. PT. XYZ has averaged during half semester of 2017 and the show end result is below the ideal value. The Ideal value refers to the value of the world class benchmark standard recommended by the Japan Institute of Plant Maintenance (JIPM) that for the Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) is 85%.

4.2 Analysis of Six Big Losses Results

Analysis of the six big losses calculation is used to determine six factors of big losses that the most contribute within the decrease machine productivity. Electrolytic Cleaning Line 1 (ECL-1) in the Cold Rolling Mill (CRM) plant.

Figure 2. Pareto Chart of Six Big Losses

The results of the six big losses are presented on the Pareto chart, it is known the biggest losses that caused of OEE has low idela value is Speed Losses Reduce factor with percent 47.1%. Reduce Speed Losses is a decrease in production speed that come up if the actual operating speed is smaller than the speed of engine that has been designed to operate on speed normal.

4.3 Analysis of Fishbone *Reduce Speed Losses*

The following is a fishbone that illustrates the cause of the high losses of reduce speed losses on the six big losses.

Figure 3. Fishbone

Based on the fishbone diagram, it is known that the cause of the high value of losses due the reduce speed losses on the Electrolytic Clean Line (ECL-1) machine consists of three main factors. There are the engine, material and method factors.

5. CONCLUSION

According to the above analysis, the researcher can make conclusions:

1. The level of effectiveness ECL-1 machine in the Cold Rolling Mill Plant (CRM) based on calculations using the Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) method which is 64.91%. if refer to the OEE ideal by the Japan Institute of Plant Maintenance (JIPM) of 85%, the level of effectiveness of ECL-1 machine is still below from ideal or can be called

- not optimal. However, based on the results of an analysis that considers the age of the machine has reached 30 years, it can be known that the OEE value is quite good.
2. Based on six big losses analysis, it is known that the root of main problem which caused by the level of effectiveness ECL-1 machine is bellow from ideal standard JIPM. The loss is found on Reduce Speed Losses with 19.80% or in the Pareto chart is 47.1 %. Meanwhile, the cause of the ECL-1 machine speed reduction is caused by machine, material and method factors.
 3. As for some suggestion to solve the research is re-evaluation of maintenance scheduling to find out a effectiveness, using spare parts with good quality, more careful supervision to minimize the risk of coil breakdown when machine speed is increased, and also making plan for related innovations or improvements that need to be done to improve effectiveness and productivity of ECL-1 machines.

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